

**PRELIMINARY RESULTS OF TECHNICAL ACCOUNTING OF
TECHNOLOGICAL FACTORS OF “CHOYSHABBOP” FABRIC.**

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Abstract. *The article developed a technical solution, and in the educational MST-910 experimental bedding items. Technical accounting of the objects of experimental weaving was carried out, the results of the factor were determined.*

Keywords: *body, arch, fabric, fabric, tex, cotton, yarn, density.*

Experimental research works were carried out on the equipment of the preparation department and weaving looms installed at the production enterprise of “Surxontex” LLC. The factors of raw material preparation for weaving, re-wrapping, sorting and carding processes were determined. During the selection process, the number of yarn breaks was determined and measures to reduce it were given. Prepared weaving reel Experimental samples of bedclothes were developed at the weaving loom of the “Surxontex” LLC enterprise. 15,4x2 tex warp yarn 100% cotton yarn was used as raw material for production of fabric samples, and 20 tex cotton yarn was used for weft yarn. The calculation of the technical shrinkage of the experimental fabric samples was performed and the results of the shrinkage factors were determined.

The fabric design process is divided into the following stages:

1. Determining the task of design, the use of fabric; technical requirements (strength, resistance to decay, flexibility, surface density, aesthetic characteristics, etc.); attention is paid to the type of finishing or the artistic decoration requirements of the fabric. For example, the following tasks are set: creating a tissue according to a certain structural phase, a given tissue surface density, increasing the wear resistance without changing the tissue surface density, low consumption of raw materials and effective surface appearance. etc. to form a tissue;
2. The compatibility of fabric construction: the selection of raw materials, the creation of a design method for the thickness of the fabric and its characteristics (filling the fabric with fibers, taking into account the change in finishing);
3. Drafting of technical documents in the production of textiles: accounting for textile ironing, equipment and technological factors of textile ironing, textile production in weaving and finishing enterprises;
4. Production of tissue samples, their testing, enterprise inspection and selection of an alternative option in the production of the tissue to be tested;
5. Creation of technical conditions for the production of new fabric at the enterprise.

From the received high-quality yarn, fabric samples were taken on the MST-910 loom and its technical calculations were made.

Same composition, cutting and filling; The ratio of the thickness of warp and weft yarns (T_T ; T_a) and their density (R_T ; R_a) is proportional. These fabrics are called similar fabrics. The

thickness of warp and weft yarns is disproportionate to their density and these tissues are called inhomogeneous.

1. Conducting sample tissue analysis and creating a complete tissue analysis program.
2. Determine the linear density (T) of the thread according to the formula; text

$$T_t = 15,4 \times 2 \text{ tex}$$

$$T_a = 20 \text{ tex}$$

The average linear density (T_{or}) of the raw material was determined.

$$T_{or} = \frac{2T_T \cdot T_a}{T_T + T_a} = 24 \text{ tex}$$

in this,

T_T – linear density of warp yarn, tex

T_a – linear density of weft thread, tex

3. Determination of the actual density of the fabric in the warp (R_t) and weft (R_a) in 1 sm, the number of threads.

4. Determination of tissue filling percentage (Z_{toq}), filling coefficient (Q_{Ntoq}) and coupling coefficient (Q_{bog}) according to the following formula:

according to warp:

$$Z_T = P_T \cdot d_T = 200 \cdot 0,22 = 43\%$$

according to weft:

$$Z_a = P_a \cdot d_a = 200 \cdot 0,18 = 42\%$$

in this,

P_T, P_a – the density of the tissue in the warp and weft;

d_t, d_a – diameters of warp and weft threads;

$$d_T = 0,0316C \cdot \sqrt{T_T} = 0,0316 \cdot 1,25 \cdot \sqrt{15,4 \cdot 2} = 0,22 \text{ mm}$$

$$d_a = 0,0316C \cdot \sqrt{T_a} = 0,0316 \cdot 1,25 \cdot \sqrt{20} = 0,18 \text{ mm}$$

in this,

C – coefficient depending on the fiber content of the yarn (indicator accepted from the reference)

The percentage of filling the fabric with warp and weft threads

$$Z_{toq} = (Z_T + Z_a) = 0,01 Z_T Z_a$$

$$Z_{toq} = 66,96\%$$

Tissue filling coefficient:

according to warp:

$$K_{ht} = \frac{P_T \cdot (R_T \cdot d_T + t_a \cdot d_a)}{100 \cdot R_T} = \frac{240 \cdot (2 \cdot 0,22 + 2 \cdot 0,18)}{100 \cdot 2} = 0,9$$

according to weft:

$$K_{ha} = \frac{P_a \cdot (R_a \cdot d_a + t_T \cdot d_T)}{100 \cdot R_a} = \frac{230 \cdot (2 \cdot 0,18 + 2 \cdot 0,22)}{100 \cdot 2} = 0,83$$

in this,

R_T, R_a – report of the tissue on the warp and weft;

t_T, t_a – the average cross section of the warp and weft threads in the rapport interval.

For tissues of order I-IV, the tissue structure phase should be less than the maximum warp and the weft should be less than the maximum value for the trunk:

–according to warp: must be greater than one ($K_{Na} > 1$)

–according to warp: must be less than one ($K_{NT} < 1$)

The structure phase should be for tissues of the VI-IX order, their density should be the maximum in the trunk, and less than the maximum in the neck

–according to warp: must be greater than one ($K_{Na} > 1$)

–according to warp: must be less than one ($K_{NT} < 1$)

For tissues of structural phase V order, the coefficient of tissue coverage should be less than one in terms of weft and fiber ($K_{NT} < 1$, $K_{Na} > 1$), because the tissue in warp and fiber the actual density should be small compared to the maximum density.

Another important indicator of fabric production on a loom is the coefficient of binding coupling coefficient:

$$Q_{bog} = \frac{P_T \cdot P_a \cdot T_{ort}}{F \cdot 1000} = \frac{24 \cdot 23 \cdot 24}{2 \cdot 1000} = 5,5$$

$$F = \frac{2 \cdot R_T \cdot R_a}{r_T + r_a} = \frac{2 \cdot 2 \cdot 2}{2 + 2} = 2$$

in this,

R_T , R_a – report of the tissue on the warp and weft;

T_T - indicator of dependence of warp and weft yarns in the rapport interval;

T_a - indicator of the relationship of warp and weft threads in the rapport interval.

The binding coefficient of linen fabrics has a high index, while satin fabrics have a low coefficient.

In sparse tissue, the coupling coefficient is small, and in dense tissue, it is high.

5. Shrinkage is the main factor that evaluates fabric in the first place in the production conditions of the loom. The shrinkage rate determines the consumption of raw materials. Shrinkage is affected by the type of raw material, the linear density of the yarn, the cross-sectional shape of the yarn, the warp, the density of the fabric on the warp and weft, the phase order of the structure, the loom factors and the production of the fabric.

The difference between the length of the thread before the weaving process and the length of the thread in the fabric is called shrinkage.

Theoretically, yarn shrinkage can be determined by the interposition of yarns within the fabric, while the following precision can be introduced.

1. The shape and cross-sectional surface of the thread should be unchanged along the total length of the fabric;
2. Two systems in the fabric are proportional to the distance between the thread centers at the intersection of the threads and the coverage coefficient of each system in the coverage.

It is planted based on the experience of shortening the threads in the fabric. A thread is pulled from a fabric sample of $10 \times 10 \text{ cm}^2$ and the length is measured, then the calculation is performed according to the formula:

according to warp:

$$a_T = \frac{L_T - B_{tuq}}{L_T} \cdot 100\% = \frac{10,4 - 10}{10,4} \cdot 100\% = 3,84\%$$

according to weft:

$$a_a = \frac{L_a - B_{tuq}}{L_a} \cdot 100\% = \frac{11,4 - 10}{11,4} \cdot 100\% = 12,28\%$$

in this,

L_T, L_a – warp and weft thread length (the length of the thread pulled from the fabric).

B_{tuq} – tissue length and width (tissue sample size in $10 \times 10 \text{ cm}^2$).

Based on the order of the experimental tissue structure phase, we found the analytical calculation and the ratio of the diameter of the threads d_T, d_a .

Wave height of threads in fabric:

according to warp:

$$h_T = \frac{d_T + d_a}{2} \cdot Q_{ht} = \frac{0,22 + 0,18}{2} \cdot 0,75 = 0,147 \text{ mm}$$

according to weft:

$$h_a = \frac{d_T + d_a}{2} \cdot Q_{ha} = \frac{0,22 + 0,18}{2} \cdot 1,25 = 0,247 \text{ mm}$$

in this,

Q_{ht}, Q_{ha} – a coefficient that takes into account the change in the wave height of warp and weft yarns depending on the phase of the fabric structure.

$$Q_{ht} = \frac{9-F}{4} = \frac{9-4}{4} = 0,75$$

$$Q_{ha} = \frac{9-F}{4} = \frac{9-4}{4} = 1,25$$

in this,

F – the order of the structural phase of the tissue (from 1 to 9).

Analysis of the obtained sample results

Table №1

Indicator name	Available fabric	Engineered fabric
Surface density of tissue, g/m^2	127	124
Linear warp of threads T_t , tex	29	15,4x2
Linear weft of threads T_a , teks	25	20
Linear density of threads, yarn/dm:		
according to warp, P_T	238	240
according to weft, P_a	220	230
Coefficient of connection	5,8	5,5
Fabric filling coefficient::		
according to warp	1,03	0,9
according to weft	0,72	0,83
Fabric filling percentage, %:		
according to warp	50	43
according to weft	35	42
Percentage of total filling of fabric, %	67,5	66,96
The diameter of the threads in the fabric, mm:		
according to warp	0,21	0,22
according to weft	0,2	0,18
Wave height of threads in fabric, mm:		
according to warp	0,15	0,147

according to weft

0,25

0,247

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